

Time for a change of guidelines for predicting neurological outcome of unconsciousness after cardiopulmonary arrest !

Comments to the draft of 2020 ERC/ESIM guidelines for post-resuscitation care

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Abstract

Background

Neuroprognostication in patients left unconscious after cardiopulmonary arrest is challenging. The recently issued draft of the 2020 ERC/ESICM guidelines for post-resuscitation care focus on predicting poor neurological outcome 3-5 days after resuscitation by means that can not be expected to perform reliably. Good outcome parameters or early-after-arrest-neuroprognosticators are not addressed.

Comments

The guideline-draft recommends to assess neuroprognosis in unconscious patients with flexor- or poorer motor responses by multimodal testing at 72 h or later after resuscitation. The heralded clinical and paraclinical tests resemble those suggested in 2015 - which failed in practice to determine the neurological outcome in a majority of patients. The approach provides indirect evidence only and does not relate to the natural history of post-arrest brain resuscitation.

None of the quintannual european resuscitation guidelines addressed good outcome parameters or early-after-arrest neuroprognosticators.

The literature informs that the rate of recovery of brain stem functions during BLS and the rate and order of appearance of concurrent neurological signs and EEG configurations within early hours after resuscitation provide definite clues to predicting poor or good neurological outcome.

Introduction of such early-after-arrest-approaches would change resuscitation strategies radically.

Conclusion

The guideline-draft focus exclusively on predicting poor neurological outcome of post-arrest unconsciousness more days after resuscitation. The prognostication strategy resembles that suggested in 2015 which did not perform reliably in practice.

This commentary points out that serial bedside investigations provide definite clues to predicting poor or good neuroprognosis within minutes to a few hours after start of basic life support.

Authoritative neuroprognostication guidelines should include clinical early-after-arrest dynamic approaches.

Background

The ultimate goal of cardiopulmonary resuscitation and post-arrest care is to restore patient's pre-arrest neurological state. Very few survivors of cardiopulmonary arrest (CA) achieve such a good outcome (GO) ¹. Since authoritative guidance to identify GO-candidates does not exist substantial numbers of patients with potential GO are presumably lost due to untimely withdrawal of life-sustaining treatment (WLST) ¹.

The draft of 2020 ERC/ESICM Guidelines for Post-resuscitation Care (d2020G) focus on *poor outcome (PO) parameters exclusively* and does not relate to the natural history of post-CA brain resuscitation. Consequently, carers may be unable to distinguish guideline-heralded-PO-signs from features of natural brain revival.

We have recently recapitulated our description of brain function recovery- or decay-characteristics after CA and the established clinical means to *predicting poor or good neuroprognosis during basic life support (BLS) and during the first hours after re-establishment of spontaneous circulation (ROSC)* ².

This commentary analyses d2020G and presents early-after-arrest neuroprognostication initiatives.

Comments

The d2020G advises to postpone conclusions about post-CA-PO at least 72 h from ROSC and, at the time of testing, to exclude influences from therapeutic hypothermia with analgesia, sedation and neuromuscular blockade (THect) that may hamper neurological examination and, to account for hemodynamic-, ventilatory- and metabolic derangements that may distort the clinical picture.

Likely PO is anticipated when two or more of the following signs are established:

Absence of pupillary light- and corneal reflexes > 72 h,
bilateral lack of N20-wave of somatosensory-evoked-potential-traces > 24 h,
'highly malignant' EEG > 24 h,
neuron-specific-enolase > 60 ug at 48 or 72 h,
status myoclonus < 72 h and
diffuse injuries on brain CT- or MR-images ¹.

The predictive elements resemble those emphasized in the 2015 guidelines ³. But, it is no longer advised to postpone prognostication 24 h if reflexes or N20-wave are present and, the times at or within or after which the tests are considered valid are modified in accordance with a recent systematic review of PO-studies ⁴.

The suggested d2020G approach will expectedly fail to determine the outcome in a majority of patients as did various versions of the 2015 algorithm when tested in practice ^{5,6}; it may perform even poorer when, in addition to other limitations ⁷, flexor-response-patients are targeted because their reaction reflects advanced brain function capacity ². Moreover, d2020G-heralded PO-indices like low voltage-, bursts-suppressions-, 'seizure'- EEG and myoclonies, may be encountered transiently during the course of natural brain revival from CA towards intact neurological survival. Repetitive checks to establish the order, rate and linkage of neurological signs and EEG are required to gauge the brain resuscitation course ². It follows that the predictive strength of e.g. a 'malignant' EEG depends on the concurrent neurology. Re-evaluations should be mandatory if contraplete neurological signs are present!

The literature provides *definite clues to assessing neuroprognosis- poor or good- early after CA*:

No recovery of cranial nerve reflexes at 30 min from start of BLS forecasts persistent unconsciousness or severe postawakening disability,
cranial nerve a-reflexia 1 h from CA predicts irreversible loss of any brain function,
failure of recovery of the ciliospinal-, caloric vestibular reflex or stereotyped motor response or losses of once recovered brain functions within 24 h signify patients who would most likely stay unconscious until final asystoli, and
brain stem a-reflexia including test-verified irreversible apnoea establishes brain death at any time after ROSC ^{2,8}.

Recovery of consciousness - advertising high odds of fair neurological perspectives- can be anticipated when
pupillary light- and ciliospinal reflexes are present within 30 min after start of BLS
or caloric vestibular reflex- and stereotyped motor responses are encountered within 1 h from ROSC.

More EEG studies have evidenced that presence of continuous cortical activity within 12 h from

ROSC relates to GO 2.

THect should be expected to blur neurology and prolong the brain resuscitation process. But, brain recovery or decay can be assessed during the setting because pupillary light- and ciliospinal reflex- and EEG-investigations are feasible 2.

Conclusion

The d2020G focus on predicting PO by late and static approaches which may fail to identify outcome in a majority of patients.

The literature informs that patients with likely poor or good neuroprognosis can be identified within minutes after CA by the rate of recovery of brain stem functions during BLS and within a few hours after ROSC by the rate and order of appearance of concurrent neurological signs and EEG configurations. Authoritative guidelines for neuroprognostication after CA should adopt early and dynamic bedside approaches.

Abbreviations

ERC/ESICM, European Resuscitation Council/European Society of Intensive Care Medicine

CA , cardiopulmonary arrest

d2020G, draft of 2020 Guidelines for Post-resuscitation Care

PO, poor outcome

GO, good outcome

WLST, withdrawal of life-sustaining treatment

BLS, basic life support

ROSC, re-establishment of spontaneous circulation

THect, therapeutic hypothermia with analgesia, sedation and neuromuscular blockade

N20-wave, scalp recorded cortical response 20 msec after stimulation of a peripheral nerve

EEG, electroencephalogram

CT, computer tomography

MR, magnetic resonance

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

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CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

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